

Biogenesis of Indole Alkaloids: A Hypothetical Common Route

(Mrs.) A. Chatterjee and S. Ghosal

A simple biogenetic scheme for indole alkaloids is advanced, attempting to unify structural patterns of compounds having diverse structural features.

The structural types found in the Indole group of alkaloids are so diverse that at one time it was thought impossible to develop a single biogenetic hypothesis encompassing all members of this group. While this could not prevent organic chemists from proposing various hypothetical schemes¹⁻³, relatively little of these has subsequently been found to be consistent with experimental results using tracers⁴⁻⁵.

In the light of currently available biochemical knowledge, a simple biogenetic scheme for indole alkaloids is therefore advanced in this communication, representing an attempt at unification of structural patterns among compounds, skeletal features of which would make them appear quite unrelated. The following scheme (Chart I) expects that slight chemical modifications of a single fundamental building block (III) would lead to all the novel structure patterns of *Voacanga*, *Tabernaemontana*, *Picalima*, *Vinca*, *Rauwolfia*, *Strychnos*, and *Alstonia* alkaloids⁶.

It is of interest to note that the indole alkaloids lend themselves remarkably well to the interpretation⁷ of their genesis from tryptophan which builds up the tetrahydro- β -carboline part of the molecule. This is a reasonable hypothesis and has been confirmed in every case where tracer experiments have been carried out⁷⁻⁹.

Much confusion has, however, been prevailing regarding the origin of the non-tryptophan-derived portion of indole alkaloids. Preliminary tracer experiments have indicated⁴⁻⁵ that this portion in the *Rauwolfia* alkaloid, ajmaline, and its congeners is formed from three acetate and one malonate units and a one-carbon fragment. Incorporation of labelled acetate was also observed in *Strychnos*⁹ and *Iboga*¹⁰ alkaloids.

Earlier hypotheses¹⁻³ assume that the non-tryptophan-derived portion of indole bases is formed by a Mannich reaction involving the α - or β -position of the indole nucleus of tryptophan (or closely related equivalent), an aldehyde, or α -keto-acid (derivable from 3,4-dioxyphenylalanine¹, perphenate², or mevalonate³), and the amino group of the tryptamine side chain. Such a condensation between (I), derived from tryptophan equivalent, and (II), formed from three acetate units, would lead in the present scheme to (III). The product (III) is considered to be the chief building unit in the genesis of indole bases.

1. Robinson, "The Structural Relations of Natural Products", Clarendon Press, Oxford, 1955.
2. Wenkert and Bringi, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **81**, 1474.
3. Thomas, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1961, No. 16, 544.
4. Leete *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **84**, 1068.
5. Leete and Ghosal, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1962, No. 25, 1179.
6. Heese, "Indol alkaloide in Tabellen" Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 1964.
7. Mothes *et al.*, *Naturforsch.*, 1959, **14B**, 355.
8. (a) Leete, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 6338; *Tetrahedron*, 1961, **14**, 35.
(b) Yamazaki and Leete, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1964, No. 23, 1499.
9. Leete, *personal communication*.
10. Leete and Yamazaki, U.P.A.C. Symposium on Natural Products, Japan (1964), Abstracts, p. 127.

Moieties (IV-VI) formed from (III) via the *N*-oxide¹¹ are the branch points *en route* to different structure patterns and presumably steer the course of subsequent transformations. Thus these combine with one malonate unit at customarily assumed sites, yielding products (VII-IX) which could then be converted to dregamine (X), ajmaline (XI), catharanthine (XII), vindoline (XIII), vincine (XIV), echitamidine (XV), strychnine (XVI), and other related alkaloids by unexceptional steps (scheme IA).

CHART I
Scheme IA.

Whereas the above alkaloids represent three essential biosynthetic consequence of combinations of (IV-VI) and malonate, no such condensation is discernible in the genesis of *Alstonia* alkaloid, echitamine (XVII), *Hunteria* alkaloid, corymine (XVIII), and *Aspidosperma* bases, olivacine (XIX), ellipticine (XX), and uleine (XXI).

It can, however, be shown by a slight variation in the sites of condensation and subsequent transformations that the same building blocks (IV & VI) would lead to bases (XVII-XXI) (Chart II, scheme 1B).

CHART II
Scheme 1B.

Although the validity of the above scheme awaits further testing with radio tracers and with the enzymes, which control these biosynthetic mechanisms, yet there are ample *a priori* reasons to advocate this as a working hypothesis for future biochemical experimentation. Thus the present scheme is fully consistent with taxonomic considerations: co-occurrence of echitamine and echitamine in *Alstonia*; olivacine, ellipticine, and uleine in *Aspidosperma*; vindoline, vincine, and catharanthine in *Vinca*, to mention a few, is a strong circumstantial evidence in favour of their genesis from common inter-

mediates. Further, there are many laboratory analogies for the dehydrogenation and transannular cyclisation reactions envisaged in the above scheme. Recently Kutney and his associates^{1,2} have demonstrated the synthesis of Ibogaine and Vincadiformine type skeleta via a novel transannular cyclisation reaction involving an ionic intermediate of type (V) (scheme 1A).

DEPARTMENT OF ORGANIC CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGES OF SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY,
CALCUTTA-9

AND
DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY OF KALYANI,
NADIA, WEST BENGAL.

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